

Original Research

A Customer Coaching Model for E-Banking Adoption in Iraq: Mixed-Method Insights

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Abstract

E-banking plays a significant role in improving the efficiency of financial services and facilitating interactions between banks and customers; however, its adoption in Iraq faces numerous behavioral, perceptual, and security-related challenges. Accordingly, the present study aims to design a customer coaching model for the adoption of e-banking in Iraq. This research employs a mixed-methods approach by integrating grounded theory and the Delphi method. In the qualitative phase, data were collected through documentary analysis and semi-structured interviews with academic experts and e-banking specialists, and analyzed using the Strauss and Corbin grounded theory approach with the assistance of MAXQDA software. In the Delphi phase, a questionnaire based on the extracted components was developed and administered to prioritize the identified factors. The findings led to the identification of four main components, namely ease of use, appropriate treatment, high security, and suitability. Among these components, ease of use was identified as the highest priority influencing the adoption of e-banking in Iraq.

Keywords: Customer Coaching, E-Commerce, Iraq Banking Sector, Technology Adoption.

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Introduction

Technological advancements in recent decades have driven the banking industry toward the extensive provision of e-banking services. e-banking refers to a set of banking services delivered through electronic platforms such as the internet, mobile devices, and digital terminals, with the aim of enhancing efficiency, reducing operational costs, and improving customer experience (Alalwan et al., 2016). Despite the substantial benefits of e-banking, numerous studies indicate that customer adoption of such services - particularly in developing countries- continues to face significant challenges (Venkatesh et al., 2016).

In Iraq, specific economic, infrastructural, and socio-cultural conditions have further complicated the process of e-banking adoption. Factors such as low levels of digital literacy, security concerns, limited trust in e-banking systems, and customers' long-standing reliance on face-to-face banking services have resulted in a considerable gap between the technological development of e-banking services and their actual usage by customers (Abed & Islam, 2022). This situation suggests that a sole focus on technological development, without adequate attention to customers' behavioral and cognitive readiness, is insufficient to achieve sustainable adoption of electronic banking.

Within the technology adoption literature, established models such as the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) emphasize that variables including perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, trust, and social influence play critical roles in shaping customers' behavioral intentions to use technology (Davis, 1989; Venkatesh et al., 2012; Venkatesh et al., 2016). However, a substantial portion of prior research has primarily concentrated on identifying adoption determinants, while paying limited attention to practical and behavioral interventions designed to facilitate technology adoption. Recent evidence suggests that educational and supportive interventions can play a decisive role in influencing customer behavior and accelerating technology acceptance (Shaikh et al., 2020).

In this context, the concept of customer coaching emerges as a novel behavioral and educational approach. In the academic literature, coaching is defined as a structured, interactive, and goal-oriented process that focuses on learning, awareness enhancement, empowerment, and behavioral change in order to improve individual performance (Grant, 2017). When applied to the context of electronic banking, customer coaching refers to a set of planned activities aimed at educating, guiding, supporting, and building customers' confidence to enable effective use of e-banking services (De Haan & Nilsson, 2023).

Recent studies indicate that continuous customer education and support, particularly in environments characterized by high uncertainty, can significantly increase the adoption of electronic financial services (Nandy et al., 2025; Shaikh & Karjaluoto, 2015). Nevertheless, a review of the existing literature reveals that a comprehensive and context-specific customer coaching model designed to enhance e-banking adoption -especially within the Iraqi context- has yet to be developed. Most existing studies have either focused on identifying adoption factors or examined customer education in a fragmented manner, with limited attention to the design of an integrated framework encompassing the key components and priorities of customer coaching.

This research gap highlights the necessity of conducting a systematic investigation that integrates behavioral, educational, and technological dimensions within a practical and coherent model. Accordingly, the present study aims to design a customer coaching model for the adoption of e-banking in Iraq. To achieve this overarching aim, the study seeks to identify the core components of customer coaching for e-banking adoption in Iraq and to prioritize these components based on their relative importance. It is expected that the findings of this research will contribute to the enrichment of the technology adoption literature and provide valuable practical guidance for bank managers and financial policymakers in promoting the sustainable development of e-banking in Iraq.

Theoretical Background and Literature Review

The present study seeks to develop a theoretical framework for understanding the role of customer coaching in enhancing the adoption of electronic banking. At the organizational level, coaching has been conceptualized as a learning and development intervention that can improve both individual and organizational performance. Recent studies have demonstrated that coaching enhances employees' skills, engagement, and effectiveness in workplace environments (Jones, Woods, & Guillaume, 2016). Meta-analytic reviews have further confirmed the effectiveness of coaching in improving individual and organizational outcomes, indicating that coaching leads to significant improvements in learning performance, attitudinal outcomes, and behavioral outcomes (Utrilla et al., 2015).

In the context of e-banking, technology adoption and digital service quality have emerged as central themes in marketing and information systems research. Electronic service quality is conceptualized as a multidimensional construct encompassing reliability, security, responsiveness, ease of use, and accessibility, and it directly influences customer satisfaction and loyalty (Ayinaddis, Taye, & Yirsaw, 2023). Empirical evidence indicates that the quality of e-banking services enhances customer satisfaction, which in turn may lead to customer loyalty (Ayinaddis et al., 2023). Similarly, a study conducted in Malaysia found that service quality attributes such as security, reliability, and responsiveness exert a positive effect on customer satisfaction, which subsequently fosters customer loyalty (Lim, Yeo, Tey, & Tan, 2023).

Within this context, the concept of perceived customer value—defined as the trade-off between perceived benefits and perceived costs—plays a critical role in the technology adoption process and customer satisfaction. Perceived value provides a basis for customers to compare their experiences with their expectations, thereby influencing their decision to continue using digital services (Zeithaml, 1988).

Customer expectations and perceptions are also regarded as key constructs in explaining satisfaction and usage behavior. Customers hold expectations regarding service quality, and the comparison between their actual perceptions and these expectations shapes their evaluation of service quality (Zeithaml, Parasuraman, & Berry, 2003). In digital environments, security, ease of use, and service responsiveness are consistently identified as key determinants in shaping perceived value and customer satisfaction (Ayinaddis et al., 2023).

Customer loyalty is defined as a customer's commitment to repeatedly use services despite the availability of alternative options, and it plays a pivotal role in the sustainable growth of banks (Ayinaddis et al., 2023). Customer satisfaction and perceived value have been repeatedly identified in the e-banking literature as essential antecedents of customer loyalty.

Despite the extensive body of research on service quality and perceived value in electronic banking, the role of customer coaching as an educational–behavioral intervention to facilitate e-banking adoption remains underexplored in the academic literature. To date, research has primarily focused on technical factors, service quality attributes, perceived value, and customer satisfaction, and no well-documented empirical studies indexed in major academic databases have explicitly examined customer coaching as a mechanism for managing e-banking adoption. Accordingly, by integrating customer coaching theory with established technology adoption and service quality frameworks, the present study addresses a significant theoretical gap in the literature.

Methodology

The present study aimed to design and explain a customer coaching model for the adoption of e-banking in Iraq and was conducted based on a pragmatic philosophy, as this philosophy emphasizes problem-solving and the generation of practical outcomes, allowing the integration of both qualitative and quantitative data (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018; Saunders et al., 2023). The study employed a mixed-methods approach, in which the qualitative phase utilized grounded theory. Data were collected through documentary analysis and semi-structured interviews with academic experts and e-banking specialists to identify the components, indicators, and relationships among them. The qualitative sample was selected based on participants' expertise, experience, and ability to provide rich insights. The sample size was intentionally limited and purposive because the objective was to obtain in-depth data for conceptual development, and interviews continued until theoretical saturation was reached, with 15 interviews.

To enhance the validity and reliability of qualitative data, in addition to independent analysis by two researchers, Triangulation of data between different sources (documents, articles, interviews) and the kappa coefficient, which was calculated to be 0.83, was used to measure agreement between analysts. (McHugh, 2012). Data were analyzed using MAXQDA through open, axial, and selective coding, forming the basis for developing the conceptual model.

After identifying the key components, in the quantitative phase, a questionnaire based on four main components (ease of use, appropriate treatment, high security, and suitability) was designed to determine the weight and priority of each component. The questionnaire included demographic questions and Likert-scale items. A total of 100 responses were considered sufficient, as the aim of this phase was to validate and prioritize the identified components, and given the limited population of e-banking experts, this sample size allowed for Delphi analysis and the achievement of expert consensus. There is no hard and fast rule regarding the selection and number of experts, and their number depends on factors such as: homogeneity or heterogeneity of the sample, the purpose of the Delphi or the scope of the problem, the quality of the decision, the

ability of the research team to conduct the study, internal and external validity, the time of data collection and available resources, the scope of the problem, and the acceptability of the response. The number of participants has usually been less than 50 (Okoli & Pawlowski, 2004).

The Delphi process was conducted over two rounds to achieve expert consensus, and the responses were analyzed using mean ranking and the Friedman test to evaluate differences in priority and ranking among the components. Components that achieved at least 70% consensus were confirmed (Gordon, 1994). This combined design enabled a deep conceptual understanding, validation of the findings, and the development of a practical, context-specific, and scientifically grounded customer coaching model for e-banking adoption in Iraq. Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of the interviewees.

Table 1: Demographic information of interviewees

No.	Position	Years	History (years)	Field of study	Education
1	Bank Branch Manager	45	23	Public Administration	Master
2	Bank Branch Manager	40	18	Marketing Management	Master
3	Bank Branch Manager	37	15	Business Management	Master
4	Senior Bank Employees	35	7	Accounting	Bachelor
5	Senior Bank Employees	37	8	Accounting	Bachelor
6	Senior Bank Employees	39	8	Business Management	Master
7	Senior Bank Employees	35	9	Project Management	Bachelor
8	Senior Bank Employees	31	8	Accounting	Bachelor
9	Senior Bank Employees	35	9	Project Management	Bachelor
10	Faculty Member	40	10	Economics	PhD
11	Faculty Member	40	10	Economics	PhD
12	Faculty Member	42	8	Business Management	Master
13	Faculty Member	40	10	Economics	PhD
14	Electronics Field Active	38	11	Business Management	Master
15	Electronics Field Active	39	12	Marketing Management	Master

Findings

The results of the open and axial coding stages of the codes extracted from the interviews with experts are presented below.

Ease of Use

In the first question after the initial discussion, the ease of use section was the most visible. According to Table 3, this main section is listed in the open coding.

Table 2: Open coding of the ease-of-use category

Basic concepts	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i	j	k	l	m	n	o	Total Number	
Complete Arabic text	1		1	1	1	1		1	1	1					1	1	10
Reducing the number of clicks		1	1	1	1		1			1	1	1	1				9
No text clutter	1	1		1				1		1	1			1	1		8
Using visual view	1		1	1		1				1					1	1	7

After summarizing and categorizing each of the aforementioned concepts, and considering semantic affinity and considering the literature studied, the axial coding of the ease of use section is as follows in Table 3.

Table 3: Axial coding of the primary concepts of the ease of use dimensions

Ease of use	Full Arabic text
	Reduce the number of clicks
	No text clutter
	Use visual view

Appropriate treatment

In the next part of the question after first speech, the appropriate treatment part was the most visible. According to Table 4, the open coding of this main section is mentioned.

Table 4: Open coding of the automatic need recognition category

Basic concepts	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i	j	k	l	m	n	o	Total Number	
Thank you message	1	1		1		1			1	1	1			1	1	1	10
Support call	1		1		1		1	1	1		1			1			8
Welcome announcement		1	1		1		1			1	1	1					7
In-person troubleshooting								1	1	1	1	1			1		6

After summarizing and categorizing each of the aforementioned concepts, and considering semantic affinity and considering the literature studied, the axial coding of the automatic need recognition section is as follows in Table 5.

Table 5: Axial coding of the basic concepts of automatic need recognition

appropriate treatment	Thank you message
	Support call
	Welcome announcement
	In-person problem solving

High Security

In the next section of the question after the first one, the high security section was the most visible. According to Table 6, the open coding of this main section is mentioned.

Table 6: Open coding of the high security category

Basic concepts	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i	j	k	l	m	n	o	Total Number
Acceptable number of passwords	1	1	1		1		1		1	1	1	1				9
No hacking and infiltration		1		1		1		1	1	1	1	1				8
Use the forget option								1	1		1	1	1	1		6
Information security										1						1

After summarizing and categorizing each of the aforementioned concepts, and considering semantic affinity and considering the literature studied, the central coding of the high security section is as follows in Table 7.

Table 7: Central coding of the basic concepts of high security

High Security	Acceptable number of passwords
	No hacking and infiltration
	Use the forget option
	Information security

Suitability

In the next part of the question after first speech, the suitability part was the most visible. According to Table 8, the open coding of this main section is mentioned.

Table 8: Open coding of the relevance category

Basic concepts	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i	j	k	l	m	n	o	Total Number
Compatibility with the phone	1	1	1	1	1						1	1	1			8
Relatively simple theme					1		1	1	1					1	1	6
No need for high memory										1	1	1	1	1		5
No need for high-speed internet		1	1	1					1							4

After summarizing and categorizing each of the aforementioned concepts, and considering semantic affinity and considering the literature studied, the axial coding of the proportionality section is as follows in Table 9.

Table 9: Axial coding of basic concepts of fit

Suitability	Compatibility with the phone
	Relatively simple theme
	No need for high memory
	No need for high-speed internet

Considering the axial coding carried out and the identified categories, the overall findings of the qualitative section can be presented as Figure 1 and 2:

Figure 1: Word cloud to present the results of the qualitative section

Figure 2: A tree diagram to present the results of the qualitative section

The initial interview results were determined as Table 10 and the Delphi technique was also implemented on it. In this way, for each finding, the sources confirming it were determined and mentioned to help its validity.

Table 10: Analysis of the interview results using the Delphi method

Factor	Sub-factor	Consistent history	Delphi 1	Delphi 2
Ease of use	Full Arabic text	Four cases	Approved	Approved
	Reduce the number of clicks	Three cases	Approved	Approved
	No text clutter	Four cases	Approved	Approved
	Use visual view	Three cases	Approved	Approved
Appropriate treatment	Thank you message	Four cases	Approved	Approved
	Support call	Four cases	Approved	Approved
	Welcome announcement	Five cases	Approved	Approved
	In-person problem solving	Four cases	Approved	Approved
High security	Acceptable number of passwords	Four cases	Approved	Approved
	No hacking and infiltration	Four cases	Approved	Approved
	Use the forget option	Five cases	Approved	Approved
	Information security	Four cases	Approved	Approved
Suitability	Suitable for the phone	Four cases	Approved	Approved
	Relatively simple theme	Five cases	Approved	Approved
	No need for high memory	Four cases	Approved	Approved
	No need for high-speed internet	Five cases	Approved	Approved

Here the qualitative part analysis is completed. With the analysis done, four factors with four sub-factors each are suggested, and a researcher-made questionnaire with valid validity and reliability was distributed among the sample members. Finally, 100 completed questionnaires were returned, which now form the basis of the quantitative part analysis.

Quantitative section

After analyzing the interview questions, a questionnaire was designed that asked the respondent's opinion on the subject in four general sections, each section having four sub-sections and each section with one question (total 16 questions). A sub-section was defined for each section, and the sub-section questions of each section were assigned to that sub-section. Finally, several sections were visited and a total of 120 people were invited to cooperate and the questionnaire was distributed among them. It is worth mentioning that the members of the interview sample were not present in the sample section of the questionnaire. The questionnaires were sent via email or WhatsApp and the answers were returned in the same way. With extensive follow-up, only 100

questionnaires were returned and were set as the research criteria. Demographic information was also asked before the main questions. Table 12 details of the respondents (number of 100 returned questionnaires) and Table 11 details of the questionnaire are given.

Table 11: Details of the respondents

Category	Description	Number of Respondents
Job Position	Bank Branch Managers	5
	Senior Bank Employees	40
	University Faculty Members	15
	Electronic Banking Specialists	15
	Other Bank Employees	25
Age	Under 25 years	13
	26–35 years	27
	36–45 years	32
	46–55 years	16
	56–65 years	12
Education Level	Bachelor's Degree	61
	Master's Degree	36
	Doctoral Degree	3
Work Experience	5–10 years	37
	11–15 years	21
	16–20 years	21
	21–25 years	7
	26–30 years	5

Based on the results presented in Table 11, the majority of respondents were senior bank employees aged 36–45 years with a bachelor's degree. Most respondents reported having between 5 and 10 years of work experience.

Table 12: Questionnaire questions and their validity

Questionnaire questions	Cronbach's Alpha	Result
16	0.82	Confirmation of validity

After going through the statistical analysis steps, the details of which were explained in the previous section, the factors presented in the model were ranked. In this section, descriptive statistics related to the research variables are presented, which include the mean and standard deviation in the section of factors affecting coaching.

Table 13: Mean and standard deviation of the scores of factors affecting banking coaching

Group	Statistical indicator	Ease	Appropriate treatment	Security	Suitability
Whole Society	Mean	4.8	2.2	1.95	1.7
	Standard deviation	0.15	0.12	0.15	0.1

The model factors should be ranked according to the data obtained, which is done by the Friedman test and the result is shown in Table 13. The results indicate that the ease of use factor has the most important effect on client guidance. After the ease factor, appropriate treatment is in second place and security is another factor. In the next place is appropriateness.

Table 14: Results of the Friedman test for ranking banking coaching factors

Group	Statistical indicator	Ease	Appropriate treatment	Security	Suitability
Whole Society	Friedman Score	4.5	4.25	2.75	2.5
	Rank	2	3	4	5

After ranking the main factors, the sub-factors were examined. Each sub-factor was measured in one question from the respondents. The ranking was done using the Friedman test, and is shown in Table 15.

Table 15: Ranking of banking coaching factors based on the Friedman test

Overall rating	Axes	Rank	Factors	Rank	Factors
1	Ease of use	1	Complete Arabic text	2	Reducing the number of clicks
		3	No text clutter	4	Using a visual view
2	Appropriate treatment	1	Thank you message	2	Contacting support
		3	Welcome announcement	4	In-person problem resolution
3	High security	1	Acceptable number of passwords	2	No hacking or intrusion
		3	Use the forget option	4	Information security
4	Compatibility with modern facilities	1	Compatibility with the phone	2	Relatively simple theme
		3	No need for high memory	4	No need for high-speed internet

Now, after ranking the main and secondary factors of importance, Delphi can be repeated for it. This part is called the quantitative Delphi and is shown in Table 16. Here, like the quantitative Delphi, the importance factors were confirmed and confirmed by the majority of respondents. The confirmation of two Delphi's in two parts indicates the strengthening of the results obtained. In different parts, each factor is categorized. However, the factors of time and proportionality of amounts overshadowed the other items.

Table 16: Delphi technique in the quantitative part

Factor	Sub-factor	Aligned respondents	Delphi 1	Delphi 2
Ease of use	Full Arabic text	1-30	Approved	Approved
	Reduce the number of clicks	24-75	Approved	Approved
	No text clutter	78-90	Approved	Approved
	Use visual view	3-26	Approved	Approved
Appropriate treatment	Thank you message	89-100	Approved	Approved
	Support call	36-100	Approved	Approved
	Welcome announcement	36-85	Approved	Approved
	In-person problem solving	58-75	Approved	Approved
High security	Acceptable number of passwords	75-100	Approved	Approved
	No hacking and infiltration	55-85	Approved	Approved
	Use the forget option	30-52	Approved	Approved
	Information security	58-69	Approved	Approved
Suitability	Suitable for the phone	75-100	Approved	Approved
	Relatively simple theme	55-85	Approved	Approved
	No need for high memory	30-52	Approved	Approved
	No need for high-speed internet	58-69	Approved	Approved

Discussion and conclusion

Technological advancements and extensive changes in service delivery methods have driven banks toward providing e-banking services. In Iraq, due to infrastructural limitations, political instability, economic challenges, socio-cultural diversity, and technological constraints, the adoption of e-banking faces unique challenges (Al Salem & Abu-Shanab, 2022). Political and security instability in recent years has reduced public trust in financial institutions, directly affecting citizens' willingness to use e-banking

services. Economically, income disparities and limited access to internet and digital devices necessitate the design of lightweight, user-friendly services to ensure inclusivity for all users (Mousa et al., 2021). From a cultural and social perspective, limited public proficiency in English and inadequate digital skills constitute major barriers to the adoption of electronic banking; therefore, customer coaching -defined as a structured process of providing continuous guidance, training, and personalized support to enhance customers' knowledge, skills, and confidence in using digital services- through simple, localized Arabic user interfaces and ongoing education and support, is considered a fundamental requirement for facilitating e-banking adoption (Grant, 2017; Venkatesh et al., 2012; Wijayati et al., 2020). Furthermore, while smartphone penetration and internet access have increased, slow internet speeds and older devices require lightweight, widely compatible software solutions (Al Salem & Abu- Shanab, 2022).

The findings of this study showed that the four main factors of the customer coaching model for Iraqi e-banking include ease of use, appropriate treatment of customers, information security, and service suitability to user needs.

Each factor included several sub-factors that were evaluated and weighted through two rounds of the Delphi technique with expert opinions. The results showed that information security had the highest priority, followed by ease of use, appropriate customer treatment, and service suitability. These findings align with the existing literature on technology acceptance and service quality, emphasizing the critical role of security and usability in fostering trust and customer loyalty (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000; Ayinaddis, Taye, & Yirsaw, 2023).

The analysis indicated that ease of use as one of the components of customer coaching for e-banking adoption in Iraq, must include simple, understandable, Arabic-language interfaces for non-English speakers. Visual displays, reduced procedural steps, and simplified operations are prerequisites for attracting new users.

Appropriate customer treatment as one of the components of customer coaching for e-banking adoption in Iraq, involves polite and friendly interactions, sending thank-you messages after each transaction, timely problem-solving, and providing both in-person and online support. These measures not only increase satisfaction but also strengthen trust and loyalty (Zeithaml, Parasuraman, & Berry, 1990).

Information security, as the primary concern of customers, requires practical measures such as data encryption, access management, intrusion prevention, and protection of personal information. At the same time, security measures should not complicate software usage; solutions for password recovery and prevention of unauthorized access are essential (Ayinaddis et al., 2023).

Service suitability as one of the components of customer coaching for e-banking adoption in Iraq, must consider user capabilities. Services should be compatible with commonly used devices and public internet, avoiding high-end hardware or high-speed internet dependency. Lightweight, simple applications ensure maximum usability, encouraging migration to electronic banking (Venkatesh et al., 2012).

In general terms, it can be concluded that the proposed customer coaching model demonstrated that focusing simultaneously on ease of use, customer-oriented behavior, security, and service suitability can significantly facilitate e-banking adoption in Iraq. The findings provide actionable insights for banks and deliver significant theoretical contributions to digital banking literature in developing countries, particularly regarding integration of customer coaching, technology acceptance, and digital service quality.

Practical Contributions

Banks should provide localized, simple, and user-friendly services based on study findings.

Implementing customer-oriented and polite behavior, including proactive support, thank-you messages, and personalized interactions, can enhance satisfaction and loyalty.

Prioritizing information security by protecting data and preventing unauthorized access strengthens trust and reduces regression to traditional banking methods.

Aligning services with realistic user conditions, including standard devices and public internet, improves access and facilitates adoption.

Theoretical Contributions

This study fills a significant gap in developing countries' literature by integrating customer coaching theories with technology acceptance and service quality frameworks.

The proposed model contributes to the knowledge of customer management, digital interaction, and banking service quality and can be generalized to other electronic services.

Findings highlight the key role of combining educational-behavioral interventions (customer coaching) with technology and user experience in successful adoption of digital services.

Limitations of this research

Differing perspectives from non-participating groups and other banks could yield different results; future studies should include larger, more diverse populations.

Potential inaccuracies in survey or interview responses were noted but were considered to have limited impact on overall findings.

Future Research Directions

Population expansion: Investigate e-banking adoption with larger samples across private, public, and regional branches to analyze demographic and regional differences.

Other electronic services: Study customer coaching in judicial, tourism, insurance, and other digital service sectors for model generalization.

Cultural and educational factors: Explore the influence of digital skills, financial literacy, and local culture on service adoption.

Longitudinal studies: Conduct long-term research to assess the impact of customer coaching interventions on customer behavior, trust, and loyalty over time.

Quantitative modeling and prediction: Apply statistical models (e.g., Structural Equation Modeling) to analyze relationships among coaching components, service quality, and e-banking adoption.

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